

2 S202T

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- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

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● S
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■ shallow
■ intermediate
■ deep
■ NA

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2 S202T

S
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shallow
intermediate
deep
NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12